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Session C

**MOLECULAR
BIOLOGY AND
BIOMEDICINE**

NUTRIGENETICS-THE FUTURE OF PERSONALIZED NUTRITION

Andriuță Carolina

*"N. Testemițanu" State University of Medicine and Pharmacy, Department of
Molecular Biology and Human Genetics, Chisinau, Republic of Moldova*

E-mail: carolina9802@gmail.com

Obesity is a multifactorial disease, with genetic polymorphisms accounting for around 70% of the population variation. Interactions between genes and nutrients can greatly influence an individual's response to diet, making it necessary for a more personalized approach in nutrition to be implemented. Associations between single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) and nutrients have been analyzed. Carriers of FADS, APOE4, ALOX5, FFAR4 gene polymorphisms have shown different patterns of lipid metabolism, each responding differently to omega-3 fatty acid supplementation.

MTHFR SNPs carriers have also shown a varying response to folate intake, which helps regulate homocysteine levels that have been associated with a higher risk of cardiovascular disease. SNPs located in the MC4R, FTO, PPAR genes have been found to influence the adherence to the Mediterranean diet. A personalized intake of macro- and micronutrients that takes into account a person's genetic background can improve the lipid profile as well as reduce inflammation, which in turn helps prevent cardiovascular disease in patients with obesity. Further research is needed to implement these findings into clinical practice.

Key words: nutrigenetics, personalized nutrition, obesity, multifactorial disease, lipid metabolism, person's genetic background.

THE INFLUENCE OF NUTRIENTS ON THE METABOLISM DEPENDING ON THE TYPE OF STRESS REACTIVITY

Babileva Anastasia

Moldova State University, Chisinau, Republic of Moldova

E-mail: anastasia.babileva@gmail.com

The experiment was performed on white rats Vistar line selected based on the reactive type of the organism (analogous to the asthenic type). For the selective choice of experimental animals with general non-specific activity of the body and with the level of stress-reactivity, the methods of "forced swimming" and "high cross-shaped labyrinth" were used. From the animals with the reactive type of the organism were formed according to the analogous principle (body mass, age, sex) 4 experimental groups of animals, of 4-5 individuals in each, which were maintained in the same conditions with an analogous diet. The difference was found in the fact that each group of animals will receive their food ration which will differ according to the caloric structure. The caloric structure of the food rations is represented in table 1. The duration of the experiment was 2 months.

Table 1. Caloric structure of food rations according to experimental groups (%)

	I group (control)	II group	III group	IV group
Proteins	8	11	12	14
Fats	35	28	27	25
Carbohydrates	57	61	61	61

Figure 1. Changing body mass depending on the caloric structure of the ration (g/animal)

Thus, according to the results obtained and presented in figure 1, allows us to make a preliminary conclusion that the best variant of the ration with caloric structure for the asthenic type of constitution is the structure of the 3rd variant: proteins -12%, fats - 27 %, carbohydrates - 61%. The biological value of food rations must be determined according to the formula of the caloric structure of the ration that reflects its balance, the type of exchange of substances of the individual and the fermentative systems that underlie it.

The formula of the caloric structure of rations is one of the most appropriate indicators. It allows to identify the optimal ratio of proteins, fats and carbohydrates - the basic energy carriers that define the nature and quality of metabolism. The health of the individual, but also possible dysfunctions and pathology depends on the ratio of these ingredients in the ration.

Key words: stress reactivity, nutrients, metabolism, ration with caloric structure, health of the individual.

IMPACT OF THE PHYTOPREPARATUS APUSET-6 ON THE ENDOCRINE PANCREAS-THYROID AXIS

Bacalov Iurie*, Crivoi Aurelia, Chirița Elena, Bîrsan Ana, Druța Adriana, Barbăroș Mihai, Revenco Andreea, Popușoi Iulia

Moldova State University, Chisinau, Republic of Moldova

*E-mail: jurabacalov@mail.ru

Thyroid hormones influence multiple metabolic processes through changes in the concentration and activity of many enzymes, the metabolism of substrates, vitamins and minerals, the rate of secretion and inactivation of other hormones and the response of target organs. Thus, the prophylaxis of the thyroid gland prevents a series of severe autoimmune diseases. In addition to drug treatment, naturist medicine is becoming more and more widespread, in order to maintain the positive effects after treatment or as a prophylactic method at an early stage. Scientific research confirms positive actions in the treatment of the endocrine-thyroid pancreatic axis. Thus, new horizons are opened in the practice of therapy and treatment of endocrine pathological conditions.

Purpose was to highlight changes in physiological indices in endocrine-thyroid pancreatic disorders in white laboratory rats against the background of APUSET-6 biopreparation.

Research object - the white laboratory rat. The model of the experimental hypothyroidism - by administering the solution of potassium thiocyanate, in a ratio of 20 mg per 100 g of body mass. The biopreparation consists of the following plants: *Anethum graveolens*, *Plantago major*, *Urtica dioica*, *Salvia officinalis*, *Equisetum arvense*, *Thymus serpyllum*.

This study highlighted the pathological effect of hypothyroidism on the body, which is manifested by disorders in all organ systems, and in late states - coma and death. Research has shown that interdependence between hypothyroidism and diabetes mellitus results in the determination of insulin hyposecretion (2.07 ± 0.17 pmol/l after administration of K⁺ thiocyanate compared to the initial concentration of 2.58 ± 0.21 pmol/l), a fact that conditions the increase in blood glucose levels (6.4 ± 0.34 mmol/l in pathology and 4.0 ± 0.22 mmol/l in the control group). The analysis of the leukocyte formula showed an increase in all indices against the background of hypothyroidism in the white laboratory rats. These changes indicate that changes in cellular immunity are closely related to the pathological conditions of the thyroid gland.

Experimentally, it has been shown that the administration of APUSET-6 biopreparation has a high efficacy in the prophylaxis of thyroid dysfunction, thus protecting the affected body from hypothyroidism, diabetes and acute infections, by maintaining hematological indices within the norm.

Key words: endocrine pancreas-thyroid axis, Apuset-6 biopreparation, physiological indices, pancreatic disorders, hypothyroidism, diabetes mellitus.

**PROPHYLAXIS OF RESPIRATORY SYNDROMES BY
NEUROIMMUNOMODULATORY ACTION OF NATURAL
ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS**

Baciu A.Ja.^{1,3*}, Mereuta I.^{1,2}, Fedas V.¹, Listopadova L.³

¹*Institute of Physiology and Sanocreatology, Chisinau, Republic of Moldova*

²*"Nicolai Testemitanu" State University of Medicine and Pharmacy,
Chisinau, Republic of Moldova*

³*Tiraspol State University, Tiraspol*

*E-mail: anatolibaciu@gmail.com

Review demonstrated particular interest on neuromodulation of inflammation, based on immunomodulatory action of parasympathetic nervous system and an indirect inhibition on the cytokine storm triggered by acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS). ARDS can be induced by direct lung injury due to bacterial or viral infection, inhalation of smoke, toxic chemicals, or aspiration of gastric contents, or indirect lung injury. Vagal neuromodulation may be a promising alternative immunomodulatory prophylaxis for respiratory syndromes due to its potent systemic anti-inflammatory effects. As a result, the release of pro-inflammatory cytokines is weakened, coagulation is modulated, and circulatory failure is prevented. The cholinergic anti-inflammatory pathway (CAIP) is a potent anti-inflammatory indirect mechanism of action on the spleen. Vagus immunomodulation is realized through the $\alpha 7nAChR$ receptor, which is found not only on neurons and macrophages, but also on other non-neuronal cells, including immune cells such as monocytes, T- and B-lymphocytes, and dendritic cells. The impact on the body of natural environmental factors is favorable due to its neuromodulatory influence, which produces an immunomodulatory effect of the parasympathetic nervous system on adaptive immunity. Urbanization and rising living standards are associated with unhealthy diet, lack of physical activity and air pollution, hypoxia, hypercapnia, noise, leading to an imbalance in the sympathetic and parasympathetic components of the autonomic nervous system.

The organization of green recreational areas, environmentally friendly urban planning, transport traffic, the exclusion of desynchronization and central fatigue during occupational activities, somatosensory stimulation are the basic components of a complex neuroimmunomodulatory preventive effect.

Key words: acute respiratory distress syndrome, autonomic nervous system, neuromodulatory influence, alternative immunomodulatory prophylaxis.

DIFFERENTIAL DIAGNOSIS OF CDG THROUGH MOLECULAR ANALYSIS OF GALT AND ALDOB GENES

Boiciuc Chiril¹, Blanita Daniela¹, Hlistun Victoria¹,
Leferber Dirk², Usurelu Natalia¹

¹*Institute of Mother and Child, Chisinau, Moldova*

²*Translational Metabolic Laboratory, Radboud UMC, Nijmegen, Netherlands*

*E-mail: tervenom@gmail.com

Errors in the synthesis, assembly and/or processing of glycans provoke a group of metabolic genetic pathologies known as Congenital Disorders of Glycosylations (CDG) that have been described at the moment around 150 types. Galactosemia and fructosemia can cause false-positive results in diagnosis of CDG due to mutation in *GALT* and *ALDOB* genes leading to changes in carbohydrate metabolism.

The aim of this study was to establish and implement the methods for molecular diagnosis of galactosemia and fructosemia necessary for differential diagnosis of CDG.

As a material for the study have been used samples of urine, DBS and DNA collected from 8 patients. Biochemical diagnosis was based on assessing of blood Galactose level, *GALT* enzyme activity and NMR spectroscopy of urine (Galactose, Galactitol and Fructose-1- phosphate). For molecular genetic diagnosis have been used PCR-RFLP and Sanger sequencing methods necessary for identification of genetic variants in *GALT* and *ALDOB* genes.

The design of primers characteristic to all exons of *GALT* and *ALDOB* genes was created with Primer3 software and checked by NCBI Primer-BLAST. Implementation of the molecular-genetic methods have been done on DNA samples of 8 patients. 7 children was suspected for galactosemia, having liver affection and sepsis (*E. coli*) after breastfeeding during the first week of life, null or reduced *GALT* activity and high urine Galactose [28.7-50.7 mol/molCrea] and Galactitol [~10 mol/molCrea]. The last one had clinical features characteristic for fructosemia, but have normal level of fructose-1-phosphate in urine, caused by his refusal to eat fruits. During molecular genetic analysis in patients with galactosemia has been identified *p. Q188R* mutation in 50% of alleles, followed by *p.E203L* (25%) and *p.K285N* (17%). It is noteworthy that 8% of alleles have not been identified yet. In the patient with fructosemia has been detected a pathological deletion (c.113-1_115del) of 4 nucleotides located in intron-exon junction between intron 2 and exon 3. This mutation could cause skipping of exon sequence during splicing of *ALDOB* gene, leading to a null activity of the residual enzyme.

The obtained results confirmed the efficiency of molecular-genetic methods in the diagnosis of galactosemia and fructosemia, that can be used successfully in the differential diagnosis of CDG.

Key words: *GALT* and *ALDOB* genes, differential diagnosis of CDG, galactosemia, fructosemia, mutation.

**BAICALEIN PREVENT SCOPOLAMINE-INDUCED MEMORY
IMPAIRMENT IN ZEBRA FISH BY INCREASING THE CREB PROTEIN
LEVEL AND THE mRNA EXPRESSION OF *BDNF*
AND *CREB* GENE**

**Brînza Ion^{1*}, Stache Alexandru¹, Eldahshan Omayma²,
Gorgan Lucian¹, Mihasan Marius¹, Hritcu Lucian¹**

¹*Department of Biology, Alexandru Ioan Cuza University of Iasi, Romania.*

²*Department of Pharmacognosy, Ain Shams University, Egypt.*

*E-mail: ion.brinza@student.uaic.ro

Baicalein (Baic), is a natural flavonoid, which was isolated for the first time from the roots of the plant *Scutellaria baicalensis*, variety, *Georgi*. Numerous studies have shown that Baic has many pharmacological properties and a variety of important biological activities such as its anti-inflammatory, anticancer and neuroprotective activity. However, its effects on the neuropathology of Alzheimer's disease (AD) have not been well studied.

Brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) is a neurotrophin with vital functions in the survival of neuronal cells. The cAMP response element binding protein (CREB) is an essential neuroprotein for long-term changes in synaptic plasticity that mediate the conversion of short-term memory to long-term memory.

This study aimed to investigate the effects of Baic pretreatment on cognitive and cholinergic deficiency, oxidative and molecular status, and neural protection against neuroinflammation in the animal model of dementia represented by zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) which was induced by immersion administration of a muscarinic cholinergic receptor blocker represented by scopolamine (Sco 100 μ M).

Baic (1, 3 and 5 μ g / L) was administered by immersion to zebrafish once a day for 16 days. To assess the level of anxiety of zebrafish we used the new aquarium diving test (NTT), to assess the spatial memory we used the Y maze test, and to assess the recognition memory we used the new object recognition test (NOR). To evaluate the effects of Baic on the oxidative and cholinergic status in the zebrafishes brain, we evaluated the specific activity of Superoxide dismutase (SOD), Catalase (CAT), Malondialdehyde (MDA) and Acetylcholinesterase (AChE) activity. Also, in this study we investigated the effects of Baic on *bdnf* and *creb* mRNA expression.

Our results show that Baic can effectively restore the antioxidant defense mechanism by increasing the level of antioxidant activity in the brain. Baic also can improve cognitive dysfunction of amnesic fish by increasing the absolute gene expression of *bdnf* and *creb* and by inhibiting AChE, which is also correlated with improved memory parameters, as shown in behavioral approaches (NTT, Y maze and NOR).

The authors state that they have no conflicts of interest.

Key words: memory impairment, Baicalein, *Danio rerio*, cognitive and cholinergic deficiency, neuroinflammation, dementia.

THE LINK BETWEEN CLINICAL MANIFESTATIONS OF SMA AND UNBALANCED GENOMIC CHANGES

Coliban Iulia^{1*}, Blăniță Daniela¹, Hadjiu Svetlana¹,
Ușurelu Natalia¹, Revenco Ninel², Sacară Victoria¹

¹*IMSP Institute of Mother and Child, Chisinau, Republic of Moldova*

²*"Nicolae Testemițanu" State University of Medicine and Pharmacy,
Chisinau, Republic of Moldova*

*E-mail: iulia.coliban16@gmail.com

Spinal muscular atrophy (SMA) is an autosomal recessively inherited progressive neuromuscular disease caused in 95% of deletions in the SMN1 gene. SMA can also be suspected along with other clinical manifestations such as mental retardation, global developmental delay, epilepsy, autism, neurological syndromes and birth defects.

We report 2 cases of 2 month and respectively 16 month boys born at term in a non-consanguineous families. Both children presented with severe hypotonia with lack of reflexes and dynamics, suggesting SMA and other clinical manifestations. The molecular-genetic examination of SMN1 gene through PCR-RFLP and qPCR methods showed deletions of exons 7 and 8 for one of them but not for the other patient. At the same time, considering other clinical manifestations associated with chromosomal genetic abnormalities, the constitutional karyotype with subsequent molecular karyotype investigation was indicated. Subsequent the result of the constitutional karyotype was normal (46 XY) for both. Molecular karyotype, through Array-CGH method, identified the following unbalanced haploinsufficient genetic changes: a 1398 Kb microdeletion in the region of chromosome 5q13.2 (of which OMIM registered genes such as SMN1, NAIP, GTF2H2, SERF associated with SMA) and a microdeletion of 4832 Kb in the region of chromosome 10q11.22-q11.23 (of which 6 morbid genes, registered OMIM) for patient without SMA diagnosed and for patient of 2 mo, with SMA diagnosed, there have been identified unbalanced genomic abnormalities (461kb duplication on chr1q and 1.78Mb deletion on chr5q, among them are the SMN1 and SMN2 genes) and regions with LOH (3.6Mb region on chr1p and 4.8Mb region on chr14q including TMEM260 gene).

In this cases, a detailed phenotypic and genotypic approach revealed that the diagnosis or suspicion of SMA was mimicked by much more complex genomic abnormalities such as microdeletion and microduplication of chromosomal sectors that are too small to be detected by conventional cytogenetic methods. Molecular karyotype is extremely important in clinical utility for patients with such genomic changes, both in diagnosis and in long-term management and the determination of the risk of recurrence. Its scientific utility is also significant, with new microdeletion or microduplication syndromes being recognized and clinically delineated.

Key words: spinal muscular atrophy, deletions of exons, chromosomal genetic abnormalities, molecular karyotype, diagnosis, long-term management, determination of the recurrence risk.

DEVELOPMENT OF METHOD FOR SHORT REPEATS EXPANSION CAUSED ATAXIAS DIAGNOSTIC

Dorif Alexandr^{1,2*}, Sacara Victoria¹

¹*IMSP Institute of Mother and Child, Chisinau, Republic of Moldova*

²*Moldova State University, Chisinau, Republic of Moldova*

*E-mail: dorif11@gmail.com

There are known many hereditary ataxias caused by short repeats expansions, most prominent of them being Huntington disease, Friedreich ataxia and a number of spinocerebellar ataxias (SCA`s).

These ataxias are very similar with each other being sometimes almost phenocopies, so a molecular-genetic diagnostic method is strictly necessary for differential diagnostics.

There is also a well-known effect called genetic anticipation, when some alleles, usually ones with a quite large, but still normal number of repeats may further expand during gametogenesis or first zygote divisions. It puts potential their children of people harboring these alleles at risk of disease development. That`s why a screening of affected child`s parents and their siblings is necessary.

A number of previously-published papers shows that number of repeats is most frequently directly correlated with age of disease onset and speed of its progression. So, counting repeats number may give not only diagnostic, but prognostic information for affected persons.

In this work we developed a diagnostic approach based on a combination of agarose gel AFLP and capillary electrophoresis-based fragment analysis to detect short repeats expansion and calculate total repeats number for a number of diseases, including different forms of SCA, Huntington disease and Friedreich ataxia. As a test group a selection of patient`s DNA with presupposed diagnosis of SCA or Friedreich ataxia stored in LGMU biobank was used. As a control group were used DNA of presumptive healthy individuals from the same biobank.

Key words: hereditary ataxias, phenocopies, genetic anticipation, short repeats expansion, repeats number for a number of diseases.

EVALUATION OF POLYMORPHISM INFORMATION OF GENETIC DIVERSITY IN BROOMRAPE FROM BULGARIA

Duca Maria, Bivol Ina*

Center of Fuctional Genetics, Moldova State University,
Chisinau, Republic of Moldova

*E-mail: bivolinga@yahoo.com

In this study, genomic polymorphism in 4 broomrape populations from different regions of Bulgaria was investigated through amplification by polymerase chain reaction of intersimple sequence repeat (ISSR) regions.

Out of 137 amplicons produced by 13 ISSR primers, 118 were found polymorphic (86.13%). The average was 10.54 fragments per primer. Moreover, ISSRs yielded 5 common and 14 specific bands. The fragment sizes ranged from 0.23 to 4 kb. This study demonstrated that 3'-anchored primers based on dinucleotide repeats with GA and AC motifs have higher polymorphism (96.43 and 100%, respectively) than primers with other di-, tri- or tetranucleotide repeats. In general, the highest number of polymorphic DNA fragments and high percentage of polymorphism were produced using primers (AG)₈YA, BC841, BC857, BC810, BC807, (CTC)₄RC and (CA)₆RG, thus demonstrating the potential of the primer system. The performance of ISSR markers used was evaluated by means of different parameters such as polymorphic information content (PIC), effective multiplex ratio (EMR), marker index (MI), Simpson's coefficient (h_i) and resolving power (RP). The PIC values for all primers varied from 0.16 to 0.35 with an average of 0.26. The highest PIC value was detected for primers (GACA)₄, BC857, (AG)₈YA (0.35, 0.33, 0.31, respectively) and lowest PIC index of 0.16 for two primers, namely, (CA)₆AC and BC835. The EMR values may be influenced by the fraction of polymorphic loci. The highest EMR was detected with the primers (AG)₈YA (17.05), BC841 (12.07), BC857 (12.00), (CAG)₅ (10.56) and the lowest was shown by the primer (CA)₆AC (0.67) with a mean EMR of 8.03 per primer. The usefulness of the system markers used was also determined by the calculation of MI for each primer. The highest MI was shown by the primers (AG)₈YA (5.35), BC857 (3.90), BC841 (3.40), (CAG)₅ (3.14) and the lowest in the primer (CA)₆AC (0.11) with a mean MI of 2.23 per primer. The discrimination potential of each primer was expressed by h_i , where the highest value was detected in BC810 (0.58) and the lowest value in (CT)₈TC (0.02). The average value of h_i for all primers (0.18) indicates that all samples are diverse and primers used are able to discriminate between all samples. The RP is the ability of a primer to differentiate between genotypes. The average RP was 8.48 per primer. The highest RP value was detected with the primer (AG)₈YA (15.04), BC841 (14.92), BC810 (14.63), (CAG)₅ (11.58), BC807 (10.04) and the lowest with the primer (CA)₆RG (1.33).

The moderate values of PIC, EMR, MI, h_i , RP parameters for the most ISSR primers could be attributed to the large genetic variability among the broomrape genotypes and/or highly informative ISSR markers used in this study.

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Key words: broomrape populations, genomic polymorphism, ISSR analysis, informative markers.

GENOME OF THE NICOTINE-DEGRADING *PAENARTHROBACTER NICOTINOVORANS* ATCC 49919

ElSabeH A.^{1*}, Honceriu I.¹, Kallabi F.^{1,2}, Boiangiu R.¹, Mihășan M.¹

¹*Faculty of Biology, Alexandru Ioan Cuza University of Iasi, Iasi, Romania,*

²*Laboratory of Human Molecular Genetics, Faculty of Medicine of Sfax,*

University of Sfax, Sfax, Tunisia

*E-mail: amadaelsabeH@gmail.com

Paenarthrobacter nicotinovorans ATCC 49919 is a nicotine degrading microorganism isolated from soil on which tobacco was cultivated. Because the bacterium uses the pyridine pathway for nicotine degradation, it could be used for the conversion of nicotine containing waste into valuable green chemicals such as 3-succinoylpyridine or 6hydroxynicotine. Here, two technologies were employed to sequence the strain's genomic DNA. Illumina NovaSeq 6000 produces short reads and, in contrast, the Oxford Nanopore Technology MinION yields long read sequences. The complete genome was obtained using the hybrid assembler Unicycler. The genome is organized in two circular replicons, the largest replicon representing the chromosome of 4 316 184 bp, with an overall GC content of 63.2%.

The second replicon measures 165 141 bp and is the pAO1 megaplasmid, with an overall GC content of 59.7%. The chromosome presented a total of 3953 coding sequences, 54 tRNAs, 2 ncRNAs, 1 tmRNA and 6 identical ribosomal operons. The plasmid shows 99.99% identity with the previously described pAO1 megaplasmid sequence (GenBank entry AJ507836.131). Low identity at the nucleotide level was found when comparing the complete genome of *P. nicotinovorans* ATCC 49919 with genomes of nicotine degrading microorganisms that also use the pyridine pathway for nicotine degradation. Hence, the complete genome sequence of *P. nicotinovorans* ATCC 49919 provides a necessary reference genome for microorganisms using the pyridine pathway for nicotine degradation and, more importantly, is an essential starting point for exploring the regulation of nicotine catabolism.

Key words: *Paenarthrobacter nicotinovorans* ATCC 49919, sequence the genomic DNA, genome organization, nicotine catabolism, pyridine pathway.

MOLECULAR ANALYSIS OF PROKARYOTIC MICROBIAL COMMUNITIES IN A TYPICAL CHERNOZEM

Frunze Nina

Institute of Microbiology and Biotechnology, Chisinau, Republic of Moldova

E-mail: ninafrunze@mail.ru

The works were carried out in 2021 in the Biotron long-term stationary experiment. 4 variants of chernozem of two land use systems were studied: arable land of fodder crop rotation with alfalfa: 1 - control, without fertilizers, 2 - mineral background, 3 - organic background (cattle manure) and a forest belt located nearby. Molecular genetic analysis was performed using the equipment of the Central Collective Use Center "Genomic Technologies, Proteomics and Cell Biology" of the All-Russian Research Institute of Microbiology, St. Petersburg, Russia.

High-throughput pyrosequencing of amplified DNA (sequencing of the M4 variable region of the 16S rDNA gene) revealed 12 types of *Bacteria* (*Proteobacteria*, *Actinobacteriota*, *Bacteroidota*, *Firmicutes*, *Acidobacteriota*, *Verrucomicrobiota*, *Planctomycetota*, *Myxococcota*, *Nitrospirota*, *Fibrobacteriota*, *Gemmatimonadota*, *Chloroflexi*) and 1 type *Archaea* (*Crenarchaeota*). The largest number of phyla (13) was noted in the soil of the control and in the soil of the mineral background. There were 12 of them in the soil of the organic background, and 11 in the soil of the forest belt. The dominant position (abundance over 10%) was occupied by 3 phyla, including 2 phyla of *Bacteria*: *Proteobacteria* and *Actinobacteriota* and archaeotes: *Crenarchaeota*. In all cases, the strongest competition between bacteria and archaea is observed, and despite the fact that archaeota are qualitatively smaller, they are in the lead everywhere, except for the soil of the forest belt. The contribution of commonly found phyla (1-5%) was 9.2-14.1% with the largest values in the soil of the organic background (14.1%) and the smallest in the soil of the forest belt (9.2%). These are usually 5 phyla: *Firmicutes*, *Acidobacteriota*, *Planctomycetota*, *Myxococcota*, and *Bacteroidota*. The total participation of rare phyla ranged from 0.98 to 1.6%. The lowest abundance was recorded by phyla of the unfertilized background, then organic and mineral backgrounds. They were 4-5 phyla: *Myxococcota*, *Nitrospirota*, *Gemmatimonadota*, *Fibrobacteriota*, and in some cases *Chloroflexi*.

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Key words: chernozem, prokaryotic microbial communities, pyrosequencing of DNA, bacteria, archaea.

**CONDITIONED REFLEX LEARNING AND MEMORY OF WHITE RATS
OF DIFFERENT AGES UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF THE BIOMASS OF
STREPTOMYCETES ISOLATED FROM THE SOILS
OF THE REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA**

Garbuzneac Anastasia^{1*}, Sheptitsky Vladimir²

¹Moldova State University, Chisinau, Republic of Moldova

²Institute of Physiology and Sanocreatology, Chisinau, Republic of Moldova

*E-mail: 11_lav_11@mail.ru

The aim of this work is a comparative study of the effect of long-term consumption of biomass of strains *Streptomyces massasporeus* CNMN-Ac-36 and *Streptomyces fradiae* CNMN-Ac-11 isolated from the soils of the central part of Moldova on the process of developing defensive conditioned reflexes and conditioned reflex memory in white rats of different ages (young and old).

The studies were performed on male Wistar rats. For 90 days animals of the experimental subgroups received daily a food supplement to the standard diet at a dose of 250 mg/kg of live weight dried biomass of two local strains of streptomycetes – *Streptomyces massasporeus* CNMN-36 or *Streptomyces fradiae* CNMN-Ac-11 grown on a nutrient medium with previously determined amino acid and lipid composition. 90 days after the animals began to consume the biomass of streptomycetes, at the age of 4 months (young) and 15 months (old), they began to develop conditioned reflexes. Rats that were fed a standard diet served as controls. To study the process of associative learning the method of developing a conditioned reaction of active avoidance of a painful stimulus was used. In order to study the processes of conditioned reflex memory the dynamics of the latent period of the avoidance reaction was determined.

It was found that long-term consumption of biomass of local strains of streptomycetes – *Streptomyces massasporeus* CNMN-36 and, to a greater extent, *Streptomyces fradiae* CNMN-Ac-11 significantly stimulates the development of a conditioned response of active avoidance in young and, especially, old animals, thereby facilitating the process of conditioned reflex learning. In addition, the consumption of *Streptomyces massasporeus* CNMN-36 biomass and, to a greater extent, *Streptomyces fradiae* CNMN-Ac-11 significantly reduces the latent period of the avoidance reaction at various times after the development of a conditioned active avoidance reaction in young and, especially, old animals, thereby contributing to slowing down the extinction of traces of conditioned reflex memory.

Thus, local strains of streptomycetes *Streptomyces fradiae* CNMN-Ac-11 (primarily) and *Streptomyces massasporeus* CNMN-36 (to a lesser extent), isolated from the soils of Moldova, are promising for further research in order to isolate and identify substances with neuroprotective and nootropic properties.

Key words: streptomycetes, conditioned reflex learning, memory, neuroprotective activity, nootropic properties.

ACTIVITY OF DIGESTIVE ENZYMES OF THE SMALL INTESTINE OF RATS WITH DIFFERENT CONSTITUTIONAL STRESS REACTIVITY

Grosul-Raileanu Olesea¹, Sheptitsky Vladimir^{2*}

¹*Moldova State University, Chisinau, Republic of Moldova*

²*Institute of Physiology and Sanocreatology, Chisinau, Republic of Moldova*

*E-mail: septitchi@mail.ru

The aim of the work is to study the activity of membrane-bound enzymes (alanine aminopeptidase, maltase, sucrase, and glucoamylase) in different parts of the small intestine of rats with different levels of constitutional stress reactivity.

Rats were divided into three groups depending on the level of constitutional stress reactivity: 1 - high stress reactivity; 2 – average level of stress reactivity; 3 – low stress reactivity. Constitutional stress reactivity was assessed using a set of behavioral tests and analysis of histopathological differences in the tissues of the stomach, thymus and adrenal glands in some animals of each group after immobilization stress. Enzyme activity was determined in the homogenates of the mucous membrane of the small intestine.

The highest values of alanine aminopeptidase activity in all parts of the small intestine were recorded in rats with low stress reactivity compared with animals with high and low stress reactivity (differences between groups reach 38%, $P < 0.05$), and the lowest values were recorded in rats with high stress reactivity except for the ileum. It should be noted that we previously recorded an increased overall proteolytic activity of the small intestine in rats with low reactivity (Sheptytsky et al., 2019). The highest activity of maltase in the parts of the small intestine with the exception of the ileum was observed in rats with an average level of stress reactivity compared to animals with high and low levels of stress reactivity, while in animals with high and low stress reactivity the values of maltase activity are similar. In the ileum the highest maltase activity was recorded in rats with high stress reactivity. The highest sucrase activity in the duodenum and proximal jejunum is observed in rats with an average level of stress reactivity compared with animals with low and, especially, high levels of stress reactivity (differences between groups reach 62%, $P < 0.05$), in the distal part of the jejunum and ileum there was a tendency to an increase in sucrase activity in rats with high stress reactivity compared to animals with high and, especially, low stress reactivity. The highest activity of glucoamylase is observed in rats with high stress reactivity in the parts of the small intestine, with the exception of the proximal part of the jejunum, where glucoamylase activity is highest in rats with medium stress reactivity, and its minimum values are observed in animals with low stress reactivity.

Thus, the results obtained demonstrate the existence of a relationship between the genetically determined stress reactivity of the organism and the digestive function of the small intestine.

Key words: membrane-bound enzymes, constitutional stress reactivity, small intestine.

MEMBRANE HYDROLYSIS OF MALTOSE IN THE SMALL INTESTINE UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF DIETS WITH DIFFERENT CONTENT OF CARBOHYDRATES IN EARLY POSTNATAL ONTOGENESIS

Mangul Olga¹, Sheptitsky Vladimir^{2*}

¹*Moldova State University, Chisinau, Republic of Moldova*

²*Institute of Physiology and Sanocreatology, Chisinau, Republic of Moldova*

*E-mail: septitchi@mail.ru

The purpose of this work is to study the membrane hydrolysis of maltose and the absorption of glucose derived from maltose in isolated loops of the rat small intestine under the influence of diets with different carbohydrate content in early postnatal ontogenesis. The studies were performed on male Wistar rats. After weaning the rat pups of the experimental groups were kept for 6 weeks on diets with a high (78.2% of energy intake) or low (27.9% of energy intake) content of carbohydrates or on a carbohydrate-free diet, then a part of the animals of each of the experimental groups were kept on a standard diet for 3 days, 2 or 6 weeks, or 4 months. Animals kept after weaning on a standard diet served as controls. For the study of digestive and transport processes, the method of perfusion of isolated loops (20 cm) of the rat small intestine in situ was used. Maltase activity was determined in the intestinal mucosa by the glucose oxidase method. It was found that a high-carbohydrate diet leads to an increase in maltose hydrolysis and absorption of the resulting glucose (by 1.2–1.5 times) depending on the initial maltose concentration (12.5; 25 and 37.5 mM). Under the conditions of a low-carbohydrate diet, the studied parameters do not change at a low concentration of maltose (25 mM) and at its higher concentrations they decrease by 1.3-1.5 times. Changes in glucose absorption are accompanied respectively by an increase or decrease in the active component of its transport. As a result of a carbohydrate-free diet there is a sharp decrease in maltose hydrolysis and especially glucose absorption (by 3 or more times). The transfer of animals from a low-carbohydrate diet to a standard diet leads to normalization of glucose absorption after 3 days and membrane hydrolysis of maltose after 2 weeks. The transfer of animals from a high-carbohydrate diet to a standard one leads only to a partial normalization of the intensity of hydrolysis and transport processes even after 6 weeks. The transfer of animals from a carbohydrate-free diet to a standard one causes a gradual increase in membrane hydrolysis of maltose and glucose absorption, however, even after 6 weeks, their intensity is 1.5 times lower than in the control group. The activity of maltase was reduced compared to the control immediately after leaving the low-carbohydrate and especially carbohydrate-free diets and, to a lesser extent, 4 months after the transfer of rats from the carbohydrate-free diet to the standard one. As a result of a high carbohydrate diet, maltase activity increases markedly and remains above the corresponding control values for the next 4 months.

Thus, long-term high-carbohydrate and carbohydrate-free diets in early postnatal ontogenesis in contrast to a low-carbohydrate diet, contribute to the development of disorders in the membrane hydrolysis of maltose and absorption of the glucose derived from maltose in the small intestine.

Key words: postnatal ontogenesis, membrane hydrolysis of maltose, absorption of glucose, diets with different carbohydrate content, development of disorders in the membrane.

THE PERSPECTIVE OF THE USE OF PREBIOTICS IN METABOLIC DISORDERS

Mereuță Ion, Leorda Ana*, Poleacova Lilia

Institute of Physiology and Sanocreatology, Chisinau, Republic of Moldova

*E-mail: leorda-ana64@mail.ru

Through metabolomics medicine, the aim is to identify the mechanisms that determine the appearance of autoimmune and chronic diseases to avoid the causes of their appearance. The breakdown of proteins, fats, carbohydrates, and fiber results, through the involvement of the intestinal microbiome, in different metabolites that have beneficial or harmful effects on the appearance of diseases: obesity, diabetes, fatty liver, etc. The paper aimed to study the impact of prebiotic substances on blood glucose levels in rats depending on the carbohydrate content in their diet.

Two complex prebiotic compositions were belabored, and their impact on the blood glucose level and body mass of laboratory rats was studied, distributed in 5 groups. The first batch received the standard ration (control), the second - composition 1, the third - composition 1 + glucose, the fourth - composition 2, and the fifth - composition 2 + glucose. The compositions included two different sources of inulin (fructan) fibers with a hypoglycemic effect, products with soluble/insoluble fiber content and enterosorbent. The results obtained show an increase in glucose content in the batch without the administration of prebiotic compositions (control), which was 7.49% compared to the initial level. After 30 days of administration of prebiotic no. 1 in group II (without glucose) - a decrease in its level was observed by 8.88%, while in group III (with glucose) - by 5.44%, compared to the content initial. Prebiotic no.2 demonstrated a higher efficacy because the glucose level, in this case, decreased in groups IV and V, respectively by - 8.61 and 10.45%, compared to the initial one. Despite the administration of glucose for 30 days, concomitantly with prebiotics in groups II and IV, an increase in body mass was observed only by 7.14 and 8.75%, being however higher compared to the control group, but lower than batches that did not receive glucose. This is due to prebiotic fibers, which facilitate the absorption of intestinal fats, leading to control of body mass. The more pronounced hypoglycemic effect of prebiotic no. 2 is explained by the role of the constituent elements. Inulin slows down digestion, allowing carbohydrate sugars to be gradually released into the bloodstream, balancing blood sugar. Co-administration of the pectin and a small amount of insoluble fiber lowers total cholesterol and low-density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol. Enterosorbents absorb harmful substances and neutralize toxins, absorb the products of the vital activity of pathogenic microorganisms, and improve metabolism.

Thus, the elaborated compositions have a different hypoglycemic effect, lead to a moderate decrease in blood glucose levels in rats, and have shown efficacy even in conditions of a major carbohydrate intake in their diet. The selected prebiotic components, serving as a substrate for the normal intestinal microbial flora, have a substantial role in the body's ability to assimilate carbohydrates (glucose tolerance) in regulating body mass, which opens the prospect of their use as a component of symbiotics in human metabolic disorders.

Key words: prebiotics, metabolic disorders, autoimmune and chronic diseases, component of symbiotics, intestinal microbial flora.

3D PRINTING MACROMOLECULAR MODELS FOR TEACHING AND DEMONSTRATION

Mihasan Marius

Alexandru Ioan Cuza University, Iasi, Romania

E-mail: marius.mihasan@uaic.ro

Advancement in three dimensional (3D) printing hardware and software makes this additive manufacturing technique rather cheap and easy to implement in schools and universities. 3D printing can be used to fabricate various teaching materials for numerous disciplines, and it has a great application in teaching life sciences. Starting with the atomic coordinates downloaded from RCSB PDB, one can create a physical model of any biomolecular structure that would help better understand/demonstrate key aspects such as molecular size, symmetry, or shape. Besides that, 3D printing of molecular models can also be used to engage students in designing their own custom printable molecule of choice, offering a great opportunity to firsthand study molecular structure. After designing and printing of more than 30 different models of molecules and macromolecular complexes (including the T7 replisome, the DNA sequencing protein nanopore, the 20S Yeast proteasome or an alpha-amylase with amylopectin), several lessons have been learned. First, surface renderings of macromolecules are extremely easy to create and print and can be tackled by any user. Surface representation of subunits of the same multimeric protein can be printed separately in different colors with a high visual impact. Unfortunately, the subunits cannot always be assembled back into the complex due to frequent overhangs and tight channels. Cartoon representations can be used only for rather small proteins as are harder to print. A higher rate of success in printing complex cartoon models can be obtained with a multilateral capable 3D printer and using soluble plastic as support. Balls and sticks models are suitable for small molecules. Printing a balls and sticks or a surface model of DNA in flexible TPU has a great visual impact when demonstrating the assembly of the nucleosome. In the end, a set of models with printing instructions are provided which could serve as a starting point for anyone wishing to print its own macromolecular models on the cheap.

Key words: 3D printing, macromolecular models, teaching, demonstration, teaching materials.

MANAGEMENT ISSUES OF CHRONIC LYMPHOCYTIC LEUKEMIA

Musteata Vasile^{1,2*}, Musteata Larisa², Coman Dana²

¹*Institute of Oncology, Chisinau, Republic of Moldova*

²*State University of Medicine and Pharmacy „N. Testemitanu”,
Chisinau, Republic of Moldova*

*E-mail: vasile.musteata@usmf.md

Chronic lymphocytic leukemia (CLL) is a substantial problem of public health and oncology due to the increase of morbidity rates, frequent and refractory relapses, development of infectious complications, often leading to poor outcomes.

The aim of the study was to determine the diagnostic features and evaluate the management outcomes of infectious complications in CLL.

The study enrolled 82 patients with CLL aged 45 to 86 years (median age 66.2 years), who were treated and followed up at the Institute of Oncology of Moldova from 2000 to 2021. There were 47 men (57.3%), women – 35 (42.7%). The diagnosis was confirmed according to the IWCLL criteria based on the study of a complete blood count with the detection of lymphocytosis $\geq 5 \times 10^9/l$, myelograms with the bone marrow infiltration $\geq 30\%$ and immunophenotyping. According to Binet Classification, 54 (65.9%) patients were diagnosed and followed up in stage A, and 28 (34.1%) patients – in stage B. The study was related to the out-patient and hospitalized care at the comprehensive cancer center.

All immunophenotyped CLL cases proved to be CD20-positive. The study of the age distribution of CLL revealed the predominance of patients aged 60-79 years. The study of the disease evolution showed that out of 54 stage A patients, 22 (40.8%) developed transformation of CLL into stage B in the period from 1 to 4 years. Transformation into stage C was revealed in 10 (35.7%) cases. The study of the frequency of infectious complications noted that in 36 (43.9%) cases there was at least one of their event. Bacterial infectious complications involved the respiratory system more commonly (29 patients, or 80.6%): acute pneumonia in 10 (27.8%), acute bronchitis in 7 (19.4%), exacerbation of chronic obstructive bronchitis in 11 (30.6%) and tuberculosis in 1 (2.8%) patient. Viral herpetic complications were diagnosed in 2 (5.6%) cases: each of them on the lips and genitals. The infectious complications with the affection of the other organs and systems were detected in 5 (13.8%) patients: in 3 (8.2%) – kidneys and urinary tract, in 2 (5.6%) – acute otitis. Over a period of 3–19 years, the fatal outcomes occurred in 16 (19.5%) patients: due to the infectious complications – in 6 (37.5%), as a result of CLL progression – in 5 (31.3%), because of the secondary tumors – in 4 (25.0%), and in one (6.2%) – due to the acute cerebro-vascular stroke. The overall survival rates after 3 and 5 years were 100% and 95.7% in stage A patients, and 84.8% and 55.4% – in stage B patients, respectively. The diagnosis of CLL was frequently proved in males aged 60-79 years due to the detection of the increased lymphocyte count in the complete blood count and bone marrow aspirate. Infectious complications may be considered as common evolution features and causes of death in CLL, especially in stage B.

Keywords: chronic lymphocytic leukemia, diagnostic features, infectious complications, increased lymphocyte count, disease evolution.

THE MODIFICATION OF FREE AMINO ACIDS RATS FED WITH PROTEIN RATION

Poleacova Lilia

Institute of Physiology and Sanocreatology, Chisinau, Republic of Moldova

E-mail: bostan-lilia@mail.ru

Proteins are known to be an essential component of most body tissues, acting as an energy substrate in the development of catabolic processes. Free amino acids in physiological fluids act as metabolic regulators, and their metabolism in the cell is extremely extensive because their amount significantly increases the number of amino acids involved in protein biosynthesis. In the literature, although enough data are known about the changes that take place in the intermediate metabolism of free amino acids, the impact of physical exertion on the background of a protein-rich diet on the body is little known. The research aim is the modification the summary content of the functional groups of free amino acids (ALL) in the blood of senile rats fed protein ration in combination with physical effort (PE).

The investigations were performed on ten white laboratory rats (males-old -24-30 months), divided into two experimental groups: group I – with protein ratio (PR) (25% - proteins, 55% - carbohydrates, 20% - lipids) without PE; group II – with protein ration with PE. The animals practiced maximum dynamic PE – swimming daily for 31 days. The water temperature is +27 °C. Duration of the experiment – 31 days. The content of free amino acids in the serum and erythrocytes was determined by the ion-exchange liquid chromatography method. The analysis of the total content of AAL was performed by functional groups, depending on the physiological role of amino acids: non-essential, essential, immunoactive, glycogenic, ketogenic, proteinogenic, and sulfur amino acids.

Analysis of the AAL serum concentration, by functional groups, in group II senile animals compared to group I, which depends largely on the absorption possibilities of enterocytes from the small intestine and partially from the large intestine, shows a decreasing tendency of the group non-essential amino acids (by 4.7%), and a significant decrease in immunoactive, essential, glycogenic, ketogenic, proteinogenic and sulfur amino acids (respectively by 48.0; 39.2; 25.7; 17.6; 36.7; 33.1%). This decrease is possibly due to disorders of the absorption processes of amino acids in food in senile animals, as well as changes in the microbiome of the small and large intestine, which actively synthesize essential AALs. The analysis of free amino acids in erythrocytes of rats from group II compared to group I identified a marked decrease in the content of amino acids. Intensive PE in senile rats causes a downward trend in the summary content of sulfur amino acids by 13.2%, and a significant decrease in other functional groups of AAL (non-essential - by 38.7%; essential - by 64.4%; immunoactive - by 48%; glycogens - by 44.7%; ketogenic - by 66.8%; proteinogenic - by 50.8%) compared to their content at animals without PE. The low content of free amino acids in the animals subjected to dynamic physical effort, fed with protein ration, is probably conditioned by the predominance of energetic mechanisms determined by PE. Thus, the impact of protein ration in association with PE in senile rats is directly related to the AAL content, depending on the functional group, in serum and erythrocytes, causing a decrease in the AAL content in all functional groups.

Key words: protein ration, modification of free amino acids, physical effort, functional groups, intermediate metabolism.

PSYCHOGENIC STRESS IN HOSPITALIZED PERSONS

Pușica Zainea

Doctoral School: Biological, Geonomic, Chemical and Technological Sciences

E-mail: pusipusi67@yahoo.com

People react very differently when they are sick and there are only weak correlations between the intensity of the immune response and disease behavior, and psychogenic stress is an obligatory component of the clinical picture when the patient is aware of the consequences of the disease to their life activities ensuring.

According to the concept of psychosomocreatology, any internal or external factor, or situation if it is assessed as significant and dangerous for oneself and others, or as interfering with daily activities, causing emotions, becomes a trigger for the development of psychogenic stress. And patients who are hospitalized are quite deeply aware of the danger of the physiological state of their organism to life activities ensuring, are highly disposed to the development of psychogenic stress, which predetermined the study of the features of its manifestation.

It has been found that the criteria for psychogenic stress in hospitalized patients are irritability, aggressiveness, disinhibition, muscle excitability, experiencing anxiety, fear, panic, phobias, difficulty concentrating, decreased attention, impaired social relationships, deviant behavior, frustration, heart palpitations or heart and breathing rate fluctuations, sleep disorders, dark thoughts, memory impairment. Hypo- and hyperkinetic variants of stress reactions are distinguished: dissociative stupor, which is manifested by sudden motor retardation, profuse cold sweating, expression of horror on the face, eyes wide open; hyperkinetic variant, exteriorizing with pronounced general agitation, psychomotor agitation, unfocused movements, chaotic autonomic reactions (tachycardia, pallor, sweating, etc.). The duration of such reactions is on average up to 48 hours; the symptoms begin to decrease on average after 6-8 hours.

In decompensated patients hospitalized for conservative treatment, psychogenic stress most often provokes the following types of disorders: 1) anxiety disorders: the patient is constantly focused on anxious thoughts and ideas, their phobia. This state differs from delirium in the fact that these ideas are quite real, and the patient cannot get rid of the fear of losing their job, incurable illness, etc. They realize that their fears are most likely unfounded, however, they cannot stop thinking about them; 2) panic disorder, characterized by sudden and causeless panic attacks - signs of uncontrolled fear. Patients experience inexplicable horror, begin to suffocate; sweating, dizziness, fear of death, tremors occur. The attack lasts from several minutes to half an hour; 3) depressive disorder - the patient is in a state of apathy, a loss of interest in everything that previously seemed important and interesting; now it seems to the patient meaningless; they see the future exclusively in black colors, are prone to self-deprecation. Depression is often accompanied by drowsiness, loss of appetite, and vegetative vascular dystonia.

Attenuation of psychogenic disorders caused by the stress of hospitalization, depending on the severity of the exacerbation of the nosological disease, should be carried out with psychotherapy or pharmacological preparations.

Key words: psychogenic stress, hospitalized persons, immune response, clinical picture, disease behavior.

ANALYSIS OF Y CHROMOSOME MICRODELETIONS AND CFTR GENE MUTATIONS AS GENETIC MARKERS IN MALE INFERTILITY

Racoviță Stela^{1*}, Moșin Veaceslav¹, Sprincean Mariana^{1,2}

¹State University of Medicine and Pharmacy Nicolae Testemitanu,
Chisinau, Republic of Moldova

²Institute of Mother and Child, Chisinau, Republic of Moldova

*E-mail: guzunstela@gmail.com

Globally it is estimated that about 15-20% of couples are affected by infertility current data from the literature show that in 50% of cases the male causal factor is involved. Genetic abnormalities cause 15%–30% of male factor infertility. Y microdeletion and CFTR gene mutations are the most frequent known molecular genetic causes associated with azoospermia and severe oligozoospermia.

The purpose of the study was to evaluate genetic markers of Y-chromosome microdeletions of the AZF and cystic fibrosis transmembrane conductance regulator (CFTR) gene mutations in azoospermic infertile men.

The study was carried out on infertile men with azoospermia recruited among infertile couples referred for reproductive treatment. All patients signed an informed consent. The endocrine markers: FSH (Follicle-stimulating hormone); LH (Luteinizing Hormone); and testosterone were evaluated. They were investigated by molecular testing for AZF and CFTR gene. Multiplex Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) was performed using Y-specific markers for AZF region: AZFa (sY84, sY86, DBY1, sY620), AZFb (sY117, sY127, sY134, SY143), and AZFc (sY254, sY255, sY153, SY158). The detections of sY14 (SRY) and ZFX/ZFY were employed as internal controls. Two common mutations $\Delta F508$ and G542X were tested of the CFTR gene.

Deletions of Y chromosome were identified in 9 (9,9%) of 91 patients with azoospermia. Deletions of AZFc - sY153, sY158, sY254 and sY255 locus were observed in four of nine azoospermic patients 55,5%. In two (22,2%) patients were detected with deletion of AZFb region, deleted markers were sY117, sY127, sY134, sY143. Deletions affecting both AZFb and AZFc loci were found in two patients 22,2%. The average level of FSH was $6,4 \pm 3,5$, LH $6,2 \pm 3,2$ and testosterone $3,3 \pm 1,4$, of patients with microdeletions. Three (3,3%) patients were identified with CFTR gene mutation $\Delta F508$, for calculating the risk of recurrence in offspring was investigated and his wife, found himself homozygous.

Molecular genetic screening is important to define the cause of spermatogenesis defect. This is important to provide a correct diagnosis and more effective solutions to couples with infertility before reproduction treatment is applied.

Key words: molecular genetic screening, spermatogenesis defect, Y chromosome microdeletions, reproduction treatment, CFTR gene mutations, genetic markers, male infertility.

MOLECULAR-GENETIC ASPECTS OF MIGRAINE

Rotaru Ludmila^{1*}, Rotaru Tudor^{2*}

¹"N. Testemitanu" State University of Medicine and Pharmacy, Department of Molecular Biology and Human Genetics, Republic of Moldova,

²"N. Testemitanu" State University of Medicine and Pharmacy, Department of Oncology, Chisinau, Republic of Moldova

*E-mail: tudor.rotaru@usmf.md, ludmila.rotaru@usmf.md

Migraine is a complex genetically determined disorder characterized by episodes of moderate to severe headaches that are estimated to affect approximately 1 billion people worldwide, predominantly women. According to the 2016 Global Burden of Disease Study, migraine is the second leading cause of disability and accounts for more disabilities than all other neurological disorders combined. Migraine is a multifactorial pathology, disabling, recurrent, neurovascular headache disorder. It can be classified into subtypes, according to the International Headache Society's headache classification committee: migraine without aura, migraine with aura and chronic migraine.

The genetic basis of migraine is complex with the involvement of several loci and genes in pathogenesis; it can rely on more than one genetic source in different genomic locations that act in tandem with environmental factors to determine the susceptibility and characteristics of the disease. Identification of mutations in the following genes: CACNA1A, ATP1A2, SCN1A, PRRT2, SLC4A4, NOTCH3 could predict targeted prophylactic treatment of migraine. Many of these genes encode proteins involved in regulating glutamate neurotransmission and the normal formation of synaptic plasticity. Molecular, anatomical, and functional modifications induce high sensitivity to homeostasis fluctuations, low adaptability in neural substrate, and recurrence of headaches. Understanding the genetic predisposition to migraine and the discovery of several susceptible gene variants and genetic polymorphism define the most compelling hypothesis for generalized neuronal hyperexcitability and generalized neuronal changes in migraines. Concerning the headache itself, studies on the understanding of molecular mechanisms show that the activation of the trigeminovascular pathway is a precondition to explain why pain is limited to the head, often affects the periorbital area and the eye and is intensifying with increasing intracranial pressure.

Changes in vascular caliber are the result of abnormal secretion of chemicals present in the brain. It has been determined that in the pathogenesis of migraine, although incompletely understood, the trigeminal nerve and its axonal projections to intracranial vascularization are involved. Nociceptive signals from the trigeminovascular system are transmitted to areas of the brain that produce the perception of migraine pain.

Key words: migraine, multifactorial pathology, nociceptive signals, genetic predisposition, generalized neuronal hyperexcitability.

USE OF AI-ASSISTED TOOLS IN HEREDITARY DISEASE DIAGNOSTIC

Sacara Victoria^{1*}, Dorif Alexandr^{1,2}

¹*IMSP Institute of Mother and Child, Chisinau, Republic of Moldova*

²*Moldova State University, Chisinau, Republic of Moldova*

*E-mail: victoriasacara@hotmail.com

One of the most difficult parts of medical genetics is analysis of a huge amount of patient's data and presumption of diagnostic. It can be even harder if we take in account multiplicity of hereditary diseases, presense of many phenocopies at some of them and purely human factors as tiredness or some form of unconscious prejudices, all of them having possibility to interfere and impair ability to put correct diagnosis, what definitively is not beneficent for patient.

This situation began to change in 1980's, when first expert systems in domain of human genetics appeared. But those systems included only limited amount of data, were statical, not able to self-improve and were composed by humans, so being influenced by all human errors.

Major changes in this field began in 2011, when FDNA company was founded and began to develop Face2Gene program, based on next-generation phenotyping and artificial intelligence technologies. This program compares patient's face photo and clinical signs with a database of previously diagnosed patients using AI and proposes a list of possible diagnoses with ranking for similarity with photo and with clinical signs.

This software helped us to diagnose such diseases as Coffin-Siris, Bloom and Myhre syndromes and much more. In this publication we summarize our experience of Face2Gene software and next-generation phenotyping use.

Key words: medical genetics, hereditary diseases, Face2Gene software, next-generation phenotyping, artificial intelligence technologies.

OVERLAP OF CLINICAL MANIFESTATIONS IN MITOCHONDRIAL DISEASES

Secu Doina*, Uşurelu Natalia, Blăniță Daniela, Sacară Victoria

Institute of Mother and Child, Chisinau, Republic of Moldova

*E-mail: secudoina95@gmail.com

Mitochondrial diseases (MD) are a clinically, biochemically and genetic heterogeneous group of disorders caused by mutations in genes that encode proteins involved in mitochondrial function. Neuropathy, ataxia, and retinitis pigmentosa (NARP) and Leigh syndrome (LS) are both established mitochondrial syndromes; sometimes the clinical manifestations in these diseases may overlap.

LS is defined as an early-onset progressive neurodegenerative MD typically characterized by subacute onset of psychomotor regression and encephalopathy associated with the development of bilateral symmetrical lesions in the basal ganglia, thalami, subthalamic regions, mesencephalon, and brainstem, which are the hallmarks of the disease. In contrast, NARP is another mitochondrial syndrome characterized by sensory axonal neuropathy, ataxia, retinitis pigmentosa, epileptic seizures, cognitive impairment, sensorineural hearing loss, diabetes mellitus, and cardiomyopathy.

Our patients manifested with recurrent seizures, muscle weakness, psychomotor retardation, feeding difficulties, elevated lactate and alanine; meanwhile, additional symptoms include exercise intolerance and partial atrophy of the optic nerve in the case of the patient with NARP syndrome, as well as tremor, ataxia and abnormal ECG in the patient with LS. Considering the multisystemic impairment and the presence of predominantly neurological clinical manifestations, an underlying mitochondrial respiratory chain disorder was suspected taking into account the clinical phenotype of the patients, and confirmed by biochemical, instrumental and genetic examinations. Evaluating the clinical criteria for mitochondrial diagnosis according to the Nijmegen Mitochondrial Disease Criteria Scale, there were counted 8 points for both patients as scoring for definite mitochondrial disorder. The first-line investigations used in this case of inborn error of metabolism indicated elevated lactate in blood [2.2-2.4 mmol/L (LS) and 3.7-7.8 mmol/L (NARP); ref. val. 0.7-2.1 mmol/L], hyperalaninemia Ala [594 μ mol/L (LS) and 1038 μ mol/L (NARP), ref. val. <450 μ mol/L], Ala/ Lys ratio [3.44 (LS) and 11.8 (NARP), abnormal if >3] and hyperaminoaciduria. Neuroimaging findings consisted of pathological foci in the bilateral basal nuclei in the case of NARP, and a symmetrical distribution of lesions along thalamus, mesencephalon, brainstem, medullary tegmentum and cerebellar hemispheres (periventricular) and medulla oblongata, in a pattern that is characteristic of LS.

Genetic analysis revealed the m.3243A>G mutation in the *MT-TL1* gene in the case of the patient with LS and in the patient with NARP syndrome the m.8993T>G mutation was identified in the *MT-ATP6* gene of the mitochondrial genome. Early onset in the presence of complete health, the polymorphism of clinical manifestations, such as a central nervous system lesion, muscle weakness, impaired psychomotor development, and seizures in a child should prompt the clinician to consider a mitochondrial disorder namely LS or NARP, and conduct further investigations such as measurement of blood lactate, magnetic resonance imaging, and if possible, genetic analysis.

Key words: mitochondrial diseases, mutations, syndrome, genetic analysis, genome.

THE BENEFITS OF L-ARGININE IN PREECLAMPSIA

Secu Gheorghe*, Secu Doina, Roșca Tamara
*State University of Medicine and Pharmacy „N. Testemitanu”,
Chisinau, Republic of Moldova*

*E-mail: secugheorghe95@gmail.com

Preeclampsia is a multisystem complex disorder with an incidence of 3-7% for nullipara and 13% for multipara and is a major contributor of both fetal as well as maternal morbidity and mortality. Endothelial nitric oxide synthase (e-NOS) promotes the synthesis of NO which dilates the arteriolar bed whereas in preeclampsia there is deficiency of e-NOS resulting in vasoconstriction of the placental vasculature as well as the vasculature of the other organs.

L-arginine is the substrate of nitric oxide (NO), a potent vasodilator, which may play a major role in regulating blood pressure. Its level in the blood during pregnancy is increased and its availability is very important to ensure proper and adequate synthesis of nitric oxide in endothelium and since there is increased destruction of NO in abnormal endothelium, the requirement of L-arginine increases.

Hypertension, proteinuria, fetal growth retardation, and glomerular damage could be induced by blockade of NO synthesis, while hypertension induced by NO synthesis inhibition could be reversed by L-arginine supplementation. Studies show that daily intravenous infusion of Arg (20 g/day) for days to women with unknown causes of IUGR increased birth weight at term by 6.4% during later weeks of gestation. In another study conducted by Neri et al., they examined the effect of L-arginine on utero-placental circulation in pregnancy complicated by intrauterine growth restriction in the third trimester and observed an enhanced level of nitrates/nitrites and the growth hormone. They also observed significant changes in various other Doppler parameters and improved fetal outcome. It was observed that after the supplementation of L-Arginine, there were significant changes in the mean values of various Doppler parameters from 1st to 3rd visit which were higher in the study group as compared to the placebo group. In different studies it has been seen that treatment with exogenous

Arginine increases fetal and neonatal outcome as well as improvements in Doppler parameters also helps in prolonging the pregnancy, but larger studies are required to further validate effects of L-Arginine. The mainstay of treatment in these patients is strict control of blood pressure using anti-hypertensive drugs and strict fetal and maternal monitoring. By examining the maternal and fetal vessels using Doppler ultrasound it is possible to determine, the risk of complications developing in the course of pregnancy long before clinical signs of preeclampsia as well as it helps in adequate fetal monitoring so that preventive and therapeutic measures can be undertaken early. L-Arginine proved to be an efficient intervention to improve the fetal and neonatal outcomes in patients with hypertensive disorders of pregnancy.

Key words: preeclampsia, multisystem complex disorder, pregnancy, L-arginine, clinical signs.

COMPARATIVE *IN SILICO* ANALYSIS OF PRIMERS USED FOR VERTEBRATE METABARCODING

Sitnic Victor

Institute of Zoology, Chisinau, Republic of Moldova

E-mail: victor.sitnic@zoology.md

DNA metabarcoding is a relatively new method of biomonitoring and refers to the molecular analysis of a mixture of intra- and extracellular DNA from various organisms. It allows the use of different target sequences for the simultaneous characterization of several organisms and has a big potential in biodiversity research. The environmental DNA (eDNA) analysis began to be applied for studying vertebrate species and like any metabarcoding research requires a correct selection of primers. In this study we aimed to perform *in silico* PCR and compare the degree of conservation, taxonomic coverage (Bc) and specificity (Bs) of 2 universal primers pairs used for vertebrate DNA analysis. The first pair (Kitano-16S) was proposed in 2006 by Takashi Kitano and co-workers as universal primers for identifying vertebrate species, based on 16S mitochondrial DNA sequencing. The second pair (12S-V5) targets the 12S mitochondrial region and was designed by Tiayyba Riaz and collaborators in 2011. The 12S-V5 has been validated using bioinformatics algorithms (*ecoPrimers*) and experimental laboratory approaches. The current study includes 191 NCBI mitochondrial genomes of 140 species of birds, 42 species of mammals, 5 species of amphibians and 4 species of reptiles, most species being part of the fauna of the Republic of Moldova.

In order to perform *in silico* analyses, there were used following bioinformatics platforms and tools: *NCBI*, *OBITools*, *ecoPCR*, *SO Ubuntu*. The assessment of the primers conservation level and graphical representation were performed using R language and *ROBITools*, *ROBITaxonomy*, *ROBIBarcodes* libraries.

The *in silico* PCR of the studied 191 mitogenomes showed that the pair Kitano-16S represents a higher degree of conservation compared to the second pair; however 12S-V5 demonstrated a clearly superior performance with a taxonomic coverage of 97.91% and a specificity of 76.47%. Respectively, for the Kitano-16S pair resulted a 21.99% taxonomic coverage and a 90.48% specificity. Also the 12S-V5 pair has a maximum of 2 mismatches for both primers while the Kitano-16S - a maximum of one mismatch for the forward primer with a total lack of mismatches for most amplicons. The metabarcodes length is about 200 bp for Kitano-16S pair and varies between 96 and 106 bp for the 12S-V5. Finally, the *in silico* amplification of the studied vertebrate mitogenomes is more efficient with the use of universal primers 12S-V5. This pair can be used to perform metabarcoding research that targets above mentioned mitochondrial genomes.

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Key words: DNA metabarcoding, biomonitoring, *in silico* PCR, mitogenomes, primers.

DIFFERENTIATION OF THE FORMS OF PHENYLKETONURIA BASED ON GENETIC DETERMINISM

**Usurelu Dan-Cristian, Scurtul Maria, Boiciuc C., Blanita Daniela,
Sacara Victoria, Usurelu Natalia**

¹IMSP Institute of Mother and Child, Chisinau, Republic of Moldova

*E-mail: dan.usurelu040599@gmail.com

Phenylketonuria(PKU) is an inborn error of metabolism, inherited in an autosomal recessive fashion resulting in >98% of cases from phenylalanine-hydroxylase(PAH) gene defect that leads to mental retardation if not treated.

Early diagnosis of PKU is possible due to neonatal screening, initiated in 1989 in the Republic of Moldova. Patient genotyping for PAH gene mutations has been used in predicting the evolution and individualization of disease treatment based on evidence from the BIOPKU database (<http://www.biopku.org>) and literature. 127 patients with PKU are registered in the Republic of Moldova. The analysis of pathogenic mutations was performed by PCR/RFLP methods and Sanger sequencing of the PAH gene. In 6 cases the DNA samples were damaged. The 121 patients, 45 genotypes were identified. Only 30 genotypes were reported in the BIOPKU database, 11 genotypes were found in the literature and 4 genotypes were not included in any of the sources. In 73.33% they corresponded to the classic PKU forms, requiring the hypophenylalanine diet as the treatment of choice, and 26.67% - Hyperphenylalaninemia. Responsiveness to BH4 was assessed based on evidence from the databases used. Thus, 5.10% of the total group were considered probably responsive at BH4, and 13.26% - responsive.

This study allows to conclude that about 20% of patients with PKU in the Republic of Moldova can be tested with BH4, with a potentially positive result, thus improving treatment with BH4 therapy. In addition, the BIOPKU database could be supplemented with the cases of 4 patients whose genotypes have not yet been registered.

Key words: phenylketonuria, genotype, neonatal screening, responsiveness to Bioppterin.